

Dynamic Context Injection in LLMs: a case study on workflow modeling

Edoardo Ramalli* and Pieter Kempeneers*

*European Commission - Joint Research Centre (JRC)

Abstract

Large Language Models can struggle to generate complex and valid technical workflows, for instance, by hallucinating parameters in structured configuration files like openEO process graphs. Existing mitigation strategies, such as long-context prompting and standard Retrieval-Augmented Generation pipelines, either overwhelm the model with noise or provide relevant information too late to support multi-step planning. This work introduces Dynamic Context Injection (DCI), a methodology that acts as an active handbook, strategically injecting specific documentation, constraints, and examples during planning and generation. Evaluated against zero-shot, context-filling, and simple RAG workflows, DCI can reduce hallucinations by enforcing stricter syntactic compliance, thus standing as a promising solution for reconciling LLM generative capabilities with rigid technical specifications.

Keywords: Context Engineering, OpenEO, GeoAI, Earth Observation, Workflow Model

Introduction

Large Language Models (LLMs) have significantly advanced the field of natural language processing. Their unprecedented semantic understanding pushes their capabilities beyond natural language generation. LLMs now act as autonomous agents equipped with tools, enabling complex reasoning and action execution. Both specialized researchers and non-expert users can leverage this technology to accelerate workflows and unlock new opportunities in fields such as Earth Observation (EO). Despite these developments, in such scientific domains, LLMs face a critical trust gap. While they possess vast embedded knowledge, LLMs are prone to hallucinating. For instance, a common problem when generating configuration files is that LLMs create syntactically convincing outputs but utilize non-existent keywords or parameters.

This challenge is particularly pronounced when using such configuration files to generate workflow models automatically. As an example, this study focuses on a workflow model for processing geospatial data using openEO (Schramm et al. 2021), a widely adopted open standard with exten-

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sive community support and documentation, but also considerable complex due to the diversity of EO tasks it enables. The openEO specification defines an API standard for processing massive cloud-based EO datasets via *process graphs*, which serve as structured JSON configuration files for data collection and processing. While LLMs are generally proficient at generating structured files in JSON format, their training data, i.e., their knowledge, can be outdated, insufficient, or not granular enough to generate specialized API configuration files. Consequently, generated outputs are frequently non-executable or fail to leverage the full range of available openEO functions, as the LLM lacks access to the openEO technical specifications during the inference phase. While we demonstrate this for the openEO specification applied to processing EO datasets, the argument holds for workflow models and the generation of configuration files in general.

Existing mitigation strategies partially address this problem. Long context prompting, i.e., filling the LLM prompt with technical documentation, is often unfeasible due to token limitations and processing inefficiency. Even when possible, it introduces noise, causing the model to lose focus during the translation of the user’s natural language intent into an openEO process graph. Conversely, Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) techniques struggle with multi-step workflow generation, causing the LLM to plan without awareness of which functions are actually available. As a result, its creative sense is unguided and cannot efficiently leverage the openEO function set. Thus, while long-context prompting overwhelms planning with excess information, RAG under-supports it by providing relevant information too late in the process.

In this setting, this work addresses a fundamental research question: How can we harmonize and optimize the LLM’s creative generalization capabilities with the rigid constraints of a technical specification? Specifically, we investigate the optimal architecture for generating valid, executable workflows from natural language prompts.

We propose Dynamic Context Injection (DCI) as a novel alternative. Unlike standard retrieval, which passively inserts text chunks into a prompt, DCI acts as an active “manual-on-the-desk”. It strategically injects specific information and examples into the prompt. By ensuring that the model has access only to the necessary information at each step of planning and generation, we aim to transform the LLM from an “uneducated” novelist into a “creative” compiler.

Therefore, the primary objective is to eliminate “creative hallucinations” by enforcing strict adherence to the specification. We evaluate this hybrid approach against zero-shot, context-filling, and RAG methods to determine which strategy best maintains semantic and syntactic accuracy. The value of this research extends beyond EO, providing a blueprint for many domains where there is a need to trade off creative problem-solving and rigid technical adherence.

Background

The performance of LLMs is tied to the management of context information available at inference time (Mei et al. 2025). This performance behavior is not monotonic; empirical evidence shows that accuracy degrades when relevant information is placed in the center of long contexts, suggesting that larger context windows are not inherently better (Liu et al. 2024).

Simultaneously, LLMs tend to hallucinate, generating ungrounded but convincing content, often because they lack information to address a task at inference time (Huang et al. 2025). This creates a *Goldilocks Zone* requirement: the context must be neither too sparse nor excessively overwhelmed by information to remain effective. This hallucinatory behavior is further accentuated by training configurations where guessing is not explicitly discouraged (Kalai et al. 2025). Furthermore, as LLMs are fine-tuned on human feedback, they tend to please the user, often prioritizing alignment with user views over critical factual verification or technical adherence (Sharma et al. 2023).

To mitigate these issues, the field of *Context Engineering* has emerged to design and manage information payloads (Mei et al. 2025). This involves three core mechanisms:

- **Prompt Engineering:** Utilizing reasoning frameworks like Chain-of-Thought (CoT) to decompose complex tasks into intermediate reasoning steps (Wei et al. 2022).
- **External Retrieval:** Addressing the limitations of static parametric knowledge by accessing dynamic databases, commonly referred to as RAG (Lewis et al. 2020).
- **Dynamic Context Assembly:** Orchestrating these components into task-optimized contexts that respect computational constraints while maximizing performance.

While LLMs demonstrate a strong capacity for generating structured outputs like JSON, studies suggest that generation tasks remain more challenging than simple conversion, particularly when strict syntactic structures are required (Yang et al. 2025). This work builds upon these results by combining prompt engineering and external retrieval to achieve Dynamic Context Injection, optimizing the model’s reasoning path within the required syntactic boundaries of the openEO specification.

Methodology

This research adopts an experimental approach to evaluate different context engineering architectures for the generation of openEO process graphs. The objective is to determine which strategy best balances the model’s generative flexibility with adherence to the openEO specifications. Figure 1 shows the experimental workflow used to benchmark four context engineering architectures for the generation and evaluation of openEO process graphs.

Dataset Curation

A benchmark dataset was developed by aggregating examples from the openEO community (Casaluce, Ramalli, and Kempeneers 2026a, 2026b). Each entry consists of a natural language user prompt paired with its corresponding valid JSON process graph. These pairs serve as the ground truth for evaluating both syntactic correctness and semantic alignment.

Experimental Design

In all experiments, we implement Chain-of-Thought (CoT) prompting as a reasoning framework. This requires the model to first generate a high-level plan, decomposing the user’s request into

Figure 1: Overview of the experimental methodology. Four different AI system architectures are evaluated for the task of openEO process graph generation, assessing syntactic and semantic correctness as well as the validity of the execution results produced by the generated configuration files.

discrete analytical steps before constructing the final openEO process graph. We compare four distinct architectures:

- **Zero-Shot (Baseline):** Relies solely on the LLM’s pre-trained parametric knowledge without external context.
- **Context Filling (Long-Context):** Fill the LLM prompt with the openEO documentation and diverse examples.
- **Standard RAG:** Utilizes a vector database to retrieve documentation chunks based on the initial user query, providing static external context.
- **Dynamic Context Injection (DCI - Proposed):** This architecture employs a two-tier retrieval strategy. The LLM is first provided with a categorical overview of the openEO library (organizing functions into families). Based on the model’s initial planning phase, specific technical schemas are injected into the context window at runtime, providing a “manual-on-the-desk” for only the active steps of the process graph construction.

Evaluation Framework

To assess performance, we utilize a multi-modal evaluation strategy:

- **Syntactic Validation:** Each generated graph is passed through the openEO Validator to check for integrity and compliance.
- **Semantic Accuracy:** An independent LLM evaluator (LLM-as-a-Judge) assesses the alignment between the ground truth and the generated output, since multiple solutions are possible.
- **Process graph execution:** where possible to run the process graph and compare the results, and measure the performance in terms of execution time.

Expected Findings and Conclusion

We expect that zero-shot and context filling will exhibit the highest failure rates due to hallucinations and information noise, respectively. While RAG provides better grounding, it is expected to lack the creative cohesion needed for complex workflows. By utilizing a two-tier retrieval approach during the reasoning process, DCI should effectively navigate the *Goldilocks Zone*, minimizing information overload while ensuring precise adherence to the technical specification.

This study aims to demonstrate that the key to trustworthy AI in specialized domains is not larger context windows, but smarter context engineering. DCI provides a robust framework for transforming natural language into valid, executable openEO process graphs, offering a scalable blueprint for any domain that requires a balance between creative problem-solving and rigid technical adherence.

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